

START

**GOOD
SCIENTIFIC
PRACTICE**

PUBLICATION FUND

**UNIVERSITY
PUBLISHING**

REPOSITORY

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

BIBLIOMETRICS + REPORTING

ACTION CARD

**COPYRIGHT
TRAP**

**GREEN
OPEN ACCESS**

GOLD
OPEN ACCESS

**DIAMOND
OPEN ACCESS**

**CLOSED
ACCESS**

OA **POLY**

OPEN ACCESS **FREE & FAIR!**

